

Basal subtype

Her2 subtype

LumA subtype

LumB subtype

Normal subtype

Basal subtype

miR-340-3p — Low - - High

Her2 subtype

miR-340-3p — Low - - High

LumA subtype

miR-340-3p — Low - - High

LumB subtype

miR-340-3p — Low - - High

Normal subtype

miR-340-3p — Low - - High

Basal subtype

miR-877-5p — Low — High

Her2 subtype

miR-877-5p — Low — High

LumA subtype

miR-877-5p — Low — High

LumB subtype

miR-877-5p — Low — High

Normal subtype

miR-877-5p — Low — High

Basal subtype

miR-940 — Low — High

Her2 subtype

miR-940 — Low — High

LumA subtype

miR-940 — Low — High

LumB subtype

miR-940 — Low — High

Normal subtype

miR-940 — Low — High

Basal subtype

miR-1307-3p — Low — High

Her2 subtype

miR-1307-3p — Low — High

LumA subtype

miR-1307-3p — Low — High

LumB subtype

miR-1307-3p — Low — High

Normal subtype

miR-1307-3p — Low — High

